

Islamic Attributes as Driving and Attracting Motivation to Maintain Tourists Loyalty at Indonesia Hospitality Tourism

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ABSTRACT

Religion tourism has a significant contribution to Indonesia's national economic development. culture, religion, and economics are covered in the global hospitality business tourism. This research aims to examine the influence of driving motivation, attracting motivations, motivations of Islamic attributes to the loyalty of visits through the satisfaction of visiting, from tourists who come to Indonesia. This article used an empirical study based on research during the COVID 19 pandemic happened. The data research was collected by 298 foreign and national tourists using purposive sampling techniques. The data is analyzed using Path analysis with SPSS software. The motivation of Islamic attributes indirectly affects the loyalty of visits (through the satisfaction of visiting) to tourists before they decide. The results highlight the importance of Islamic attributes related to Indonesia tourism, that contributes several contributions: 1) as a theoretical contribution, religion still takes place in everyone decisions, 2)

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as a tourism industry, there are many efforts to increase tourist satisfaction and loyalty to their visits, 3) as a policy-making contribution, the Indonesian government needs to improve marketing strategies that will ensure satisfaction and encourage tourists to come again.

ملخص

تساهم السياحة الدينية بصورة كبيرة في التنمية الاقتصادية الوطنية في إندونيسيا. ويتم تغطية كل من الثقافة والدين والاقتصاد في السياحة العالمية المبنية على خدمات الضيافة. ويهدف هذا البحث إلى دراسة تأثير الدوافع المحركة، ودوافع الجذب، والدوافع المبنية على أساس الصفات الإسلامية على ولاء الزوار من خلال الرضى على الزيارة من قبل السياح القادمين إلى إندونيسيا. وقد استخدم هذا المقال دراسة تجريبية تستند إلى بحث أجري أثناء جائحة كوفيد-19. وجمعت بيانات البحث من 298 سائحاً أجنبياً ومحلياً باستخدام تقنيات أخذ العينات الهادفة. ثم خضعت للتحليل باستخدام تحليل المسار بمساعدة برنامج الحزمة الإحصائية للعلوم الاجتماعية (SPSS). وكنتيجة، وجد أن دافع السمات الإسلامية يؤثر بشكل غير مباشر على ولاء الزوار (من خلال الرضى على الزيارة) حتى قبل اتخاذ السياح لقرار السفر. وتسلط النتائج الضوء على أهمية السمات الإسلامية المتعلقة بالسياحة الإندونيسية والتي تساهم بعدة أشكال: 1) مساهمة نظرية، لا يزال الدين عاملاً من عوامل اتخاذ القرارات للجميع، 2) صناعة سياحية، هناك العديد من الجهود لزيادة رضا السياح وولائهم، 3) مساهمة في صنع السياسات، تحتاج الحكومة الإندونيسية إلى تحسين استراتيجيات التسويق التي تضمن الرضا وتشجع السائحين على العودة مرة أخرى.

ABSTRAITE

Le tourisme religieux a une contribution significative au développement économique national de l'Indonésie. La culture, la religion et l'économie sont couvertes dans le tourisme d'affaires de l'hôtellerie mondiale. Cette recherche vise à examiner l'influence de la motivation motrice, les motivations d'attraction, les motivations des attributs islamiques à la fidélité des visites par la satisfaction de visite, des touristes qui viennent en Indonésie. Cet article a utilisé une étude empirique basée sur les recherches effectuées lors de la pandémie COVID 19. Les données de recherche ont été collectées auprès de 298 touristes étrangers et nationaux en utilisant des techniques d'échantillonnage intentionnel. Les données sont analysées à l'aide de l'analyse Path avec le logiciel SPSS. La motivation des attributs islamiques affecte indirectement la fidélité des visites (par la satisfaction de la visite) aux touristes avant qu'ils ne se décident. Les résultats soulignent l'importance des attributs islamiques liés au tourisme en Indonésie, qui apportent plusieurs contributions : 1) en tant que contribution

théorique, la religion prend encore place dans les décisions de chacun, 2) en tant qu'industrie touristique, de nombreux efforts sont déployés pour accroître la satisfaction des touristes et les fidéliser à leurs visites, 3) en tant que contribution à l'élaboration des politiques, le gouvernement indonésien doit améliorer les stratégies de marketing qui garantiront la satisfaction et encourageront les touristes à revenir.

Keywords: Attracting Motivation, Driving Motivation, Islamic Attributes, Visit Loyalty, Visit Satisfaction

JEL Classification: O1, Z3

1. Introduction

Tourism is a significant foreign exchange source for the global economy (Al-Ansi et al., 2019; Arts, 2020). The tourism industry covering destinations, hospitality, and culinary has become a significant economic activity that associates the meaning of satisfaction for customers of all circles, religions, ethnicities, and socio-economic backgrounds (Williams, 2006). Religion tourism, as a new paradigm in the hospitality industry, is growing as the nation needs in the global era (Boğan & Sarıışık, 2019; Heidari et al., 2018). As an Islamic majority country, Indonesia needs to examine how religion can affect tourism management in hospitality and spirituality (Ghaderi et al., 2020). Hospitality provides an excellent experience to customers in travel, accommodation, food and drink, and general event management (Ghaderi et al., 2020; Helena et al., 2019). The emotional value and quality value that arises in tourism services significantly affect tourist's satisfaction and loyalty, both domestically and internationally (Yang et al., 2014).

The number of tourist visits to Indonesia continues to increase year on year (Figure 1). The increase in tourist visits is an indicator of the success of the Indonesian government in managing tourism. Managers should encourage the tourism sector to better business competitiveness and more competitive advantages (Chiang & Shyu, 2016). The idea of destinations with exotic scenery and service quality based on religious values strongly influences tourists' decision to visit (Al-Ansi & Han, 2019). Increasing tourist visits significantly impact Indonesia's foreign exchange financial profit, country image, business creativity, community welfare, cultural development, and so on.

Figure 1: Increasing Number of Foreign Tourists to Indonesia 2020 (BPS, 2020)

Tourism contributed significantly to the country's foreign exchange in Indonesia from 2016 to 2018 (Figure 2). Manufacturers get a good market. As owners of hotels, restaurants, and transportation, they have a competitive advantage. Competitiveness in the tourism industry is a popular research topic that is very beneficial for sustainability. Competitiveness in the tourism industry is a popular research topic that is very beneficial for sustainability and business development (Cronjé & du Plessis, 2020). Business development (Cronjé & du Plessis, 2020) tourism contributed significantly to its foreign exchange from 2016 to 2018 in Indonesia.

Figure 2: Total Foreign Exchange Tourism Sector (Billion US\$) (BPS, 2020)

The satisfaction that tourism business managers can provide to "sell" aspects of tourism in terms of places, scenery, weather/climate, services, facilities, culinary, etc., has encouraged tourists to visit and "return" to visit tourist destinations. Social and psychological factors such as expression, behavior, needs, and external environments such as natural conditions, weather, culture, and social group interactions determined tourist satisfaction (Bayih & Singh, 2020). The tendency of travelers to find locations that match expectations, motivations, desires, memorable experiences, and of course, financial capabilities is a very profitable business opportunity (Cronjé & du Plessis, 2020). Two dimensions of universally accepted motivation are very related factors of encouragement and attraction, causing tourists motivation to visit a destination (Aziz et al., 2018). This research will contribute to building a unified strategy between religion and the tourism industry. The study aims to fill the gap by testing Islamic attributes with other factors that attract tourists to visit Indonesia.

In this article, researchers report the results of studies conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. Several stages were carried out in this study, namely, the first stage is the stage of identification of problems in the field where Islamic attributes and motivations affect the loyalty of tourists in the pandemic period. The second stage is the search for theories as to the basis for determining variables, hypothesis making, and questionnaires. The third stage is the test questionnaire (pre-test) which its validity and reliability. The fourth stage is the dissemination of questionnaires through Google forms sent through WhatsApp and emails to respondents, namely foreign and national travelers using purposive sampling techniques. At this stage, 298 respondents sent back questionnaires. The fifth stage is data analysis using Path analysis techniques with SPSS software. The sixth stage is discussed and confirmed with previous similar studies. The seventh stage is inference. The eighth stage is the preparation of articles, and publications.

2. Literature Review

The development of the tourism industry continues to be driving through service position activities. Managers in the tourism industry determine their marketing management strategy based on a traveler's commitment to visit again and recommend tourism destinations and experiences they receive to other potential visitors (Bayih & Singh, 2020). The experience

depends heavily on human relations, tourist perception, hotels, culinary, transportation services, souvenir shops, art performances, and worship facilities (Tomej & Xiang, 2020). Tourism management should consider material and spiritual elements to provide tourists' satisfaction (Heidari et al., 2018). Religiosity moderates the relationship between generic motivation to tourists' preferences through the Satisfaction of Islamic services obtained by tourists (Hassani & Moghavvemi, 2019). Value is a critical factor for developing long-term relationships with local or foreign consumers and gaining a competitive edge for business tourism (Shakoori & Hosseini, 2019).

Update this research by developing Eid & El-Gohary's (2015) research by replacing moderator variables, Islamic religiosity with mediator variables, and the visit's satisfaction. He developed Al-Ansi & Han's (2019) research by adding visit satisfaction as a mediator variable, replacing the analysis test tool using path analysis. Expanded Al-Ansi et al. (2019); Bayih & Singh's (2020); Choi et al. (2016); Cronjé & du Plessis' (2020) researches, by adding motivational attributes of Islam as independent variables. Developed Collins-Kreiner's (2020) research by adding visit loyalty as an independent variable.

2.1 Driving motivation

Tourist has various motivations for visiting destinations. Knowledge of destination choice encourages marketers to predict each destination's objective characteristics on offer (Helena et al., 2019). Managing services for tourists' satisfaction is the main requirement for developing motivation to revisit or recommend specific destinations. Tourists maximize their satisfaction and expectation in making travel decisions by choosing the best alternatives from various aspects such as emotional experience, saturation, stress, vacation, longing, etc. (Helena et al., 2019; Wattanacharoensil & La-oruual, 2019; Yang et al., 2019).

2.2 Attracting Motivation

Tourists decide to go on a tour also influenced by motivations that attract interests such as the beauty of destinations, ritual traditions, hospitality, culinary, shopping, food, promotion on social media, dance, social interaction, transportation, and so on (Barcelos et al., 2019; Choi et al., 2016; Erb, 2013; Hew et al., 2018; Ko & Kim, 2015; Romão et al., 2014). The Socio-cultural, socio-demography, and ethnic diversity of the

community is also an attraction for tourists. Tourists have an unforgettable experience of the socio-cultural values of people living in tourist destinations, both local and global (Aziz et al., 2018).

2.3 Islamic attribute motivation

Religion is one of the most common motivations for tourists to travel. A religiously motivated journey, one of the oldest forms of mobility globally, continues to grow (Collins-Kreiner, 2020; Terzidou et al., 2018). Religion and spiritual tourism even occupies the main tourism segment that tourists love in various countries (Heidari et al., 2018; Iliev, 2020). Worship facilities for Muslims and non-Muslims, halal food, and fashion purchases, religious sites become spiritual attributes that affect tourists' spirituality when traveling (Awan et al., 2015; Hassani & Moghavvemi, 2019; Ismanto et al., 2021). Islamic religiosity has a significant effect on tourist satisfaction levels (Ghaderi et al., 2020). Religiosity plays an essential role in the relationship between variable beliefs and the behavior of purchasing goods and services for global Muslim consumers (Eid & El-Gohary, 2015; Mura & Wijesinghe, 2019). Religious sites offer visitors various experiences, including religious services, buildings such as mosques, churches, temples, choir performances, musical performances, and religious ceremonies (Hughes et al., 2013).

2.4 Visiting Satisfaction

The tourists' satisfaction has significant confirmation of the expectation of the quality of service and travel experience. Tourist satisfaction is significantly influenced by the attracting Motivation and the driving Motivation according to the level of the tourist experience and the level of tourist expectation (Helena et al., 2019; Sato et al., 2018). The level of category comparison between expectations and satisfaction should be in the same order to demonstrate tourism management's success in meeting visitors' expectations competitively (Romão et al., 2014). Tourists maximize satisfaction by capturing the potential results of the affordability of actualizing tourism components such as destinations, facilities, services, information, and prices, such as their target interests and expectations (Tomej & Xiang, 2020). Tourism managers must classify and analyze which types of values tourists want from their destinations, such as natural environments, food, art performances, legends, weather, souvenir crafts, ritual traditions, and so on. The entire market can be segmented and selected based on the desired value

preference (Yang et al., 2014). Value preferences from individual travelers will result in different destination choices and satisfaction levels than other traveler segments.

2.5 Visiting Loyalty

Tourist visits' loyalty is closely related to tourist visits' satisfaction with previous satisfaction experienced by themselves and other tourist experiences. The repurchasing of a consumer's goods and services and providing recommendations to potential consumers next illustrates consumer loyalty in the marketing literature (Yoon & Uysal, 2005). Loyalty is such a complex concept that it is difficult to define expressly. Travelers' faithful behavior towards tourist destinations is analyzed in two categories: recommendations and repurchases (Niemczyk, 2014).

3. Research Model

The tourism literature, driving and attracting motivation, and religious attributes provide a theoretical basis for studying Islamic attributes' motivating factors to visit loyalty through satisfaction. This study examined the effect of towing motivating factors (X1), thrusters (X2), Islamic attributes (X3) on Visit loyalty (Z) through Visit satisfaction (Y). The research framework is illustrated in Figure 3.

To formulate the hypothesis on driving motivation, attracting motivation, and Islamic attribute motivation towards visit loyalty with visit satisfaction as an intervening variable, a research model presented in Figure 3 is required.

Figure 3: Research model

4. Hypothesis development

The three-factor theory is the classification of product and service attributes based on how customers view those attributes and their impact on customer satisfaction (Gregory & Parsa, 2013). According to the International Genealogical Index states, driving motivation is a person's mental state, the fulfillment of needs and desires that can be considered one of the psychological influences of tourists' behavior. The tension of one's mind and inner self from the routine of work, making wanting to refresh and relax by vacationing or visiting tourist attractions (Bayih & Singh, 2020). It can restore physical and spiritual freshness, enjoy time with family, enjoy the uniqueness of cultural rituals and natural beauty (Cronjé & du Plessis, 2020).

The driver's motivation starts with intention; psychology and social circumstances significantly affect the visit's loyalty (Bayih & Singh, 2020). Thus, a person's psychological condition when experiencing stress and boredom requires physical and spiritual freshness through vacation. Tourist destinations are offered if tourists and tourists feel happy, do not pray, and do not pray. Then, tourists will be loyal and visit again or recommend to friends and relatives.

H 1: Driving motivation affecting Visit Loyalty

Prospect Theory identifies consumer behavior through various aspects of decisions (Kahneman et al., 2009). This theory describes individuals' decision-making processes in risky conditions based on different values of profit and loss influenced by perceived potential value rather than the final result. Travelers consider the availability of attributes at their destination. These attributes usually refer to common attributes such as safe tourist attractions, the availability of complete facilities such public transportation, hotels, travel agencies, places of worship, culinary specialties, historical sites, beautiful nature, and hospitality of local people.

The destination can influence the satisfaction of tourists (Boit & Doh, 2014). Destination venues should consider common attributes accompanied by accommodation, food, festivals, convenience, and travel package prices (Ragavan et al., 2014). Mussalam dan Tajeddini (2016) divides the driving into four categories: the brand reputation of the destination, the attraction of tourism, tourism infrastructure, and tourism

services (Mussalam & Tajeddini, 2016). Tourists are happy with the destination visited, so they want to visit again and recommend the destination.

H 2: Attracting Motivations are affecting Visit Loyalty

Islam and tourism are based on the Qur'an 29:20, which encourage people to travel on earth to take lessons from God's creation and take His mercy. Islamic Tourism is defined as a tourist trip intended to provide tourism services and facilities for Muslim tourists following Islamic rules (Al-Ansi & Han, 2019). According to Battour et al. (2010) that the motivation of Islamic attributes consists of physical and non-physical aspects; physical aspects include the availability of worship facilities (mosques/mosques, Qur'an and qibla, Muslim-friendly toilets) and halal food. At the same time, non-physical attributes include Islamic entertainment, Islamic sharia-compliant clothing, adherence to Islamic morality, and the presence of adhan's voice (Battour et al., 2010). Eid & El-Gohary (2015) suggested that non-physical attributes of the availability of separate services according to gender, the presence of entertainment, sharia arts. Fajriyati's et al. (2020) research states that there are four dimensions of Islamic attributes in halal tourism destinations: worship facilities, halal food, alcohol and gambling, and Islamic morality. The more Islamic attributes are available in tourist attractions, Muslim tourists are easy to carry out worship, feel safer, and believe because the procedures carried out in tourist attractions according to Islamic Sharia to increase tourists' loyalty are expected to visit again.

H3: Islamic Attributes Motivations are affecting Visit Loyalty

Prospect Theory identifies consumer behavior through various aspects of decisions (Kahneman et al., 2009). This theory describes individuals' decision-making processes in risky conditions based on different values of profit and loss influenced by perceived potential value rather than the final result. The results of Al-Ansi & Han's (2019) research state that motivation is driving: a person's intentions, psychological condition, and social circumstances have a significant effect on visit satisfaction and visit loyalty. The uniqueness of cultural rituals, natural conditions, and the number of beautiful destinations in a city can increase tourists' desire to visit again because tourists feel satisfaction and feel happy when visiting, so recommend the destination to the broader community (Collins-Kreiner,

2020). Barcelos et al. (2019) suggest that tourists who feel satisfaction after visiting a destination will recommend and promote the place through social media.

H4: Driving motivation is indirectly affecting Visit Loyalty through Visit Satisfaction

Kahneman et al. (2009) found that the state on the individual so that alternative good name decisions is not always consistent and rational. The purpose of the Prospect Theory is to make decisions if there is uncertainty at the time of choice. Fajriyati's et al. (2020) research proposes that complete tourist destination facilities and good service make tourists comfortable and happy so that the driver's motivation affects the visit's satisfaction. Collins-Kreiner (2020) states that tourists are interested in visiting tourist destinations based on the completeness of the facilities and the hospitality of the local community, the environmental security of tourist destinations, social conditions, and cultural arts. All of them will become tourists' attractions to keep visiting again because vacationing and learning about the local culture. The competitiveness of tourism is an essential aspect in considering the development of a destination, with one of the efforts is the promotion in a relentless way (Cronjé & du Plessis, 2020).

H5: Attracting motivation is indirectly affecting Visit Loyalty through Visit Satisfaction

Hertzberg et al. in Fajriyati et al., (2020) suggested that Three-Factor Theory was a development of the Two Factor Theory that was first formulated in the context of employee satisfaction. The two-factor theory identifies that employees will only be motivated to do their job to the fullest if they are satisfied with their work. Employee satisfaction level will depend on two factors, namely hygiene factors (motivators) (Smith & Deppa, 2009). Kano, et al. in Rotar & Kozar (2017) states that the Kano model is known as a three-factor customer satisfaction theory. It generally classifies product and service attributes based on how customers view attributes and their impact on customer satisfaction.

The motivation of Islamic attributes with the availability of worship facilities (Battour et al., 2010). According to Collins-Kreiner's (2020) research, not only a facility of worship that affects a person's religion, with morality according to Islamic sharia, the entertainment of Islami, the

sound of azan diligent sounded, modesty in a dress can give a happy feeling for Muslim tourists. Four dimensions of Islamic attributes in halal tourism destinations are worship facilities, halal food, alcohol and gambling-free, and Islamic morality (Fajriyati et al., 2020). The more Islamic attributes make Muslim tourists are easy to carry out worship and feel safer. The procedures are carried out in tourist attractions following Islamic sharia so that when on holiday with sufficient time, tourists' satisfaction will increase and then increase tourists' loyalty, visit again, and recommend to the public through social media.

H6: Islamic Attribute motivation is indirectly affecting Visit Loyalty (through Visit Satisfaction)

5. Research Methodology

The study used quantitative methods. This research uses survey techniques by distributing questionnaires to respondents, namely tourists visiting Bali and Yogyakarta's tourist destinations. Bali and Yogyakarta are famous destinations for Indonesian tourism. This research refers to the research framework Patwardhan's et al. (2020) research. This research builds a research model to investigate the motivations of tourists visiting Indonesia until deciding to repeat the visit and give recommendations to others. Each factor will be analyzed to find which factors most affect travelers' motivation and vice versa. The illustrated research model is in Figure 3.

The participants selected are tourists who have visited tourist destinations in Bali and Yogyakarta. The COVID 19 pandemic caused the number of tourists to decrease due to the travel ban and the closure of some destinations. The number of tourists visiting is uncertain, so determining the number of samples to be used in this study uses the following Rao formula:

$$n = \frac{z^2}{4 (moe)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1,96^2}{4 (0,1)^2}$$

$$n = 96,04$$

Description;

n = number of sample

Z = confidence interval required in the research at $\alpha = 5\%$, $Z = 1,96$

moe = margin of error (maximum tolerated error of 10%)

Based on the Rao formula, a sample of 96 people was chosen from the population. The study used purposive sampling techniques. The sample that responded to the study numbered 298 respondents spread in Bali and Yogyakarta. The questionnaires that the respondents had filled out were analyzed all to get more accurate results.

Table 1: Participant Profile

Variable	N (Total Respondent) = 298	Percentage
Sex		
Male	177	59.39
Female	121	40.60
Age		
16-30 Years old	154	51.67
31-45 Years old	74	24.83
>45 Years old	70	23.48
Education Level		
Elementary School	5	1.77
Junior High School	22	7.80
High School	124	43.97
Freshgraduate	109	38.65
Postgraduate/doctoral	22	7.80
Job		
Student	95	32.42
Private Employee	75	25.59
Civil Employee	52	17.74
Entrepreneur	52	17.74

Variable	N (Total Respondent) = 298	Percentage
Housewife	12	4.09
Army	6	2.04
Other	1	0.03
Mean of expenditure		
< Rp 1,000,000	95	32.09
Rp 1,000,000 – Rp 2,400,000	82	27.70
Rp 2,400.000 – Rp 5,000,000	66	22.29
>Rp 5,000,000	53	17.90
Nationality		
Indonesia	250	83.8
Amerika	6	2.01
Netherlands	9	3.02
Austria	3	1
Australia	9	3.02
India	2	0.67
Perancis	3	1
Spanyol	2	0.67
Japan	1	0.33
Malaysia	1	0.33
Thailand	10	3.35
Italia	1	0.33
Germany	1	0.33

This research used questionnaire surveys as instruments. Questionnaires were collected to get information from respondents per question item according to the issues studied, where questionnaires were created in the google form. Respondents received the google forms abroad via email and WhatsApp. This online way took because researchers experience physical distancing until the area closure or tourism place during the pandemic period. The literature studies were used to obtain secondary data.

This study adopts several variables, the influence of attracting motivation such as saturation, desire to gather, relax (Hew et al., 2018); driving motivations such as destination beauty, traditional rituals, hospitality, culinary, shopping (Choi et al., 2016); motivation of Islamic attributes such as prayer facilities, halal food, halal fashion (Battour et al., 2010); loyalty such as the desire to visit again and recommend destinations to relationships (Niemczyk, 2014; Pinkus et al., 2016); the satisfaction of visiting such as the suitability of the service with expectations (Yang et al., 2014).

6. Results and analysis of the study

Based on the ANOVA or F test, the result is 361,248 which is significantly at the level of $0.000 < (\alpha) = 0.05$, so it can be said that the motivation of Islamic attributes encourages motivation, and motivation attracts significantly affects visit satisfaction (see Table 3). This test verifies that three motivating factors are acceptable for analyzing satisfaction.

The regression analysis results explain that independent variables that are motivational encouraging, interesting motivations have no significant effect on visiting satisfaction, at levels 0.473 and 0.249, respectively. Attractive motivation significantly affects visiting satisfaction at $0.000 < 5\%$ used in this analysis (see Table 4). Examples of attracting motivations include tourists' motivations (refresh, enjoy the unique culture of Yogyakarta, and Bali people, convenient transportation, a variety of interesting travel packages, various and complete destinations, such as nature, culinary, shopping, cultural destinations).

Based on ANOVA test or F test with results at 357,599 with a level of $0.000 (< (\alpha) = 0.05)$. It can be said that the satisfaction of visiting, the motivation of Islamic attributes, motivation encourages, motivation attracts significantly affects the loyalty of the visit (see Table 5). Although all items are related to travel preferences, some things focus more on the Islamic dimension; Islamic services, Islamic products, and hedonistic behavior avoidance preferences (pornography, gambling, and nightlife).

Based on the ANOVA or F test with results at 357,599 with a rate of $0.000 (< (\alpha) = 0.05)$, the visiting satisfaction, motivation of Islamic attributes, motivation spurring, attractive motivation significantly affect visit loyalty

(see Table 6). The regression analysis results can be explained that motivation encourages, motivational attractive, motivational attributes of Islam affect the loyalty of visits at a rate of 0.000 each substantially; 0,000; 0,001; 0,000. A value significantly < 5% was used in this study (see Table 7).

Figure 4: Driving, Attracting, Islamic Attribute Motivation, Visiting Satisfaction, and Visiting Loyalty

6.1 Confirmatory factor analysis

The quality of the data in the hypothesis test will affect the results of the test accuracy. The validity and reliability testing assess the quality of data.

6.2 Validity Test

The validity test measured the validity of the questionnaire. The comparing the sig (2-tail) value with alpha, so the statement is said to be valid if the sig (2-tail) value is < alpha 0.05 performed the validity tests.

6.3 Reliability Test

The Alpha Cronbach coefficient with an Alpha Cronbach value of 0.908 each; 0,973; 0,949; 0,921; 0,919 tested the reliability of the research instruments.

6.4 Classic Assumption Test

The normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test conducted the classic assumption test. The test result was that the data

distributed normally with a value of Asym Sig (2-tailed) of 0.123; the data did not occur multicollinearity with a tolerance value of > 0.1 and a VALUE of VIF < 10 . The data also did not happen heteroscedasticity with an alpha value greater than 0.05.

Table 2: Structural Model Testing

Sig	Description	Hypothetical acceptance/rejection
0,000	The driving Motivation variable directly influences Visit Loyalty.	hypothesis one is accepted.
0,000	Attracting the Motivation variable directly influences Visit Loyalty.	hypothesis two is accepted.
0,001	Islamic Attribute Motivation variable directly influences Visit Loyalty.	the third hypothesis is accepted.
0,473	Driving Motivation indirectly influences Visit Loyalty (through Visit Satisfaction)	hypothesis four is rejected.
0,000	Attracting Motivation indirectly influence Visit Loyalty (through Visit Satisfaction)	hypothesis five is accepted.
0,249	The Islamic Attribute Motivation indirectly influences Visiting Loyalty (through Visit Satisfaction)	the sixth hypothesis is rejected.

6.5 Sobel Test Analysis

Sobel test analysis of service quality variables (X) on visitor satisfaction variables (Z) through visitor loyalty (Y) and sobel test analysis of rate variable (X) to visitor satisfaction variable (Z) through visitor loyalty (Y) used in this study is a sobel test. Sobel test analysis of service quality variable (X) to visit loyalty variable (Y) through visit satisfaction (Z) and sobel test analysis of rate variable (X) to visitor satisfaction variables (Z) through visitor loyalty (Y) used in this study is a sobel test.

Figure 5: Sobel Test of Attracting Motivation to Visit Loyalty through Visit Satisfaction

Based on the results of calculations in the Sobel Test Calculator application for the significance of Mediation t calculate the value of 4,769 greater than t table 1,968, significance level of 0.05, and two-tailed probability value of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus visit satisfaction significantly mediates the influence of attracting motivation on visit loyalty.

6.6 Path Analysis

Regression Analysis of Influence of Driving Motivation, Attracting Motivation, and Islamic Attribute Motivation on Visit Satisfaction–Equation 1.

The direct influence of Driving Motivation, Attracting motivation, and Islamic Attribute Motivation on Visiting Satisfaction is explained in the following regression equation model 1:

Table 3: ANOVA Result for Model 1

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	4176,211	3	1392,070	361,248	,000b
Residual	1132,930	294	3,854		
Total	5309,141	297			

a. Dependent Variable: Visiting Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Islamic attribute motivation, driving Motivation, attracting Motivation.

Based on ANOVA test or F test that the result is 361,248, which is significantly on level $0,000 < (\alpha) = 0,05$, it can be said that Islamic attribute motivation, driving motivation, attracting motivation significantly influence visiting satisfaction.

Table 4: Coefficients^a of Model 1

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	,796	,396		2,008	,046
Driving motivation	,011	,015	,039	,718	,473
Attracting motivation	,202	,015	,816	13,402	,000
Islamic attribute motivation	,018	,016	,047	1,155	,249

a. Dependent Variable: Visiting Satisfaction

The results of the regression analysis explained that the independent variables, namely DM (Driving Motivation), AM (Attracting Motivation), are not significantly influenced to VS (Visiting Satisfaction) for each on levels 0,473 and 0,249. The attracting motivation significantly

affects VS (Visiting Satisfaction) on level 0,000 or < 5 %, used in this analysis.

Tabel 5: Model Summary of Model 1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,887a	,787	,784	1,96303

Predictors: (Constant), Islamic attribute motivation, driving motivation, attracting motivation.

The output of the summary model above shows that the value of R² for this equation is 0,787. $\sqrt{(1-R^2)}$ calculated the value of e₁. So the value of $e_1 = \sqrt{(1-0,787)} = 0,461$.

Regression Analysis of Effects of Driving Motivation, Attracting Motivation, Islamic Attribute Motivation and Visit Satisfaction on Visit Loyalty - Equation II

The direct influence of Driving Motivation, Towing Motivation, Islamic Attributes Motivation, and Visit Satisfaction on Visit Loyalty can be explained in the following regression equation II model:

Table 6: ANOVA Result of Model 2

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1634,676	4	408,669	357,599	,000b
Residual	334,844	293	1,143		
Total	1969,520	297			

a. Dependent Variable: Visiting loyalty

b. Predictors: (Constant), visiting satisfaction, Islamic attribute motivation, driving motivation, attracting Motivation.

Based on ANOVA test or F test with a result on 357,599 by a significantly level on 0,000 ($\alpha = 0,05$). It can be said that visiting Satisfaction,

Islamic attribute motivation, driving motivation, attracting motivation significantly influence visiting loyalty.

Table 7: Coefficients of Model 2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-1,446	,217		-6,654	,000
Driving motivation	,043	,008	,264	5,424	,000
Attracting motivation	,051	,010	,336	4,861	,000
Islamic attribute motivation	,028	,008	,121	3,282	,001
Visiting satisfaction	,159	,032	,261	5,010	,000

a. Dependent Variable: visiting loyalty

The driving motivation (DM), attracting Motivation (AM), Islamic attribute motivation (IAM) significantly influence Visiting Loyalty (VL) on level for each 0,000; 0,000; 0,001; 0,000 explained by the result of regression analysis. A significant value < 5 % was used in this research.

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,911a	,830	,828	1,06902

Predictors: (Constant), Islamic attribute motivation, driving motivation, attracting motivation

The summary model results above show that the value of R^2 for these two equations is 0,830. $\sqrt{(1-R^2)}$ calculated the value of e_1 . The amount of the value $e^2 = \sqrt{(1-0,830)} = 0,412$.

7. Discussion and implications

The results of hypothesis 1 in this study are in line with Bhuiyan et al., (2016) research, which states that a person's psychology while in saturation, a lot of pressure makes the need to rest and visit a tourist destination. Tourists will return to revisit the tourist destination so that the driving's motivation significantly affects the visit's loyalty.

The results of hypothesis 2 in this study are in line with Choi et al. (2016), and Cronjé & du Plessis' (2020) researches. They stated that tourism development with massive promotion could become a tourist attraction to visit the destination. According to the research of Al-Ansi & Han (2019) found that the availability of worship places makes tourists feel comfortable and not confused about performing worship, mostly Muslim. Ageeva & Foroudi's (2019) and Collins-Kreiner's (2020) stated that the identity of the nation and the uniqueness of the culture, the customs of the community could be the attraction of tourist visits to visit again so that the motivation of the driving has a significant effect on the loyalty of the visit.

The results of hypothesis 3 in this study are in line with Akhtar et al. (2019); Al-Ansi & Han's (2019) researches. They stated that halal restaurants' availability in a tourist destination is a plus so that tourists will visit again. According to the research of Akhtar et al. (2019), and Al-Ansi & Han (2019), they found that the motivation of Islamic attributes has a significant effect on the loyalty of visits.

This study is not in line with Huang & Pearce's (2019) research, which suggests that Muslim tourists have difficulty finding halal food and worship places. This research is similar to Hughes et al. (2013) research, which states that historical sites such as Cathedral in the UK offer architecture and typical Cathedral artworks to increase spiritual levels. The religious, historical places focus only on religious tourists' facilities even though different religions can visit the tourist destination. It is difficult for Muslim tourists to carry out religious orders when traveling to Muslim minority tourist destinations.

The results of hypothesis 4 in this study showed that the number of Muslim settlers feels unhappy and dissatisfied when visiting tourist attractions because it is influenced by facilities that are less concerned

with aspects of halal tourism destinations. This research is not in line with Al-Ansi & Han's (2019), Bayih & Singh's (2020), and Fajriyati's et al. (2020) researches. They stated that motivations such as intention, psychological and social circumstances could be essential to restore the state of physic and spiritual with one of the tours. Al-Ansi et al. (2019) research found that tourists who are happy to have vacationed to a tourist destination and feel satisfaction then feel loyal to revisit because all the needs of tourists' psychology can be met and recommend to the broader community. The driver's motivation does not affect the visit's loyalty through the visit's satisfaction.

The results of hypothesis 5 in line with Barcelos et al. (2019) research that good governance of tourism management can attract tourists to visit again. Ageeva & Foroudi's, (2019), Al-Ansi et al. (2019), and Ali et al. (2020) researches mentioned that attracting motivation such as facilities, services, the local community's state, and environmental security affect the motivation to tourist satisfaction and revisit. Thus the motivation of the driving affects the loyalty of the visit through the satisfaction of the visit.

This research is not in line with Iliev's (2020) research, which states that religious tourist destination facilities must maintain existing history, sites, and culture to sustain local uniqueness and wisdom. The development of halal tourism is not significant in the religious tourism of the Muslim minority state.

The results of the hypothesis of 6 studies are in line with Fajriyati et al.'s (2020) research, which states that the Motivation of Islamic attributes does not affect visitation satisfaction. Bali situation, an international tourist destination, and most local people are non-Muslim and many non-Muslim tourists. Hence, there is still a lack of awareness for halal tourism development, evidenced by even many lodgings that provide alcoholic beverages instead of mineral water.

This research is not in line with Akhtar et al.'s (2019), Al-Ansi & Han's (2019), Eid & El-Gohary's (2015) researches. They mentioned that a tourist destination with the availability of halal food, places of worship, separate public toilets, qibla signs make it easy for tourists to carry out religious orders. Thus the motivation of Islamic attributes does not affect the visit's loyalty through the visit's satisfaction. Tourism is becoming a global industry that is very important for both developing and developed

countries. According to Rangus' (2016) research that the importance of tourism is that it has been widely discussed and analyzed through comprehensively dedicated research, seminars, and conferences to impact the vast tourism industry on the local, national and global economies.

The study shows that tourism in Indonesia leads tourists' motivation on Islamic services and Islamic products affect the loyalty of tourist' visits significantly. These findings suggest that the motivation of Islamic attributes significantly affects the satisfaction of tourist visits. According to the research of Hassani & Moghavvemi (2019), and Yang et al. (2019) which stated that religion affects a person's cognition and psychological well-being, which, in turn, affects a person's choice of goals and product preferences. These results are consistent with previous research of Patwardhan et al. (2020) which showed a link between religion, loyalty, satisfaction, and motivation of tourists.

The results underscore the critical role of Islamic values on tourism behavior and influence the decision-making process of each component of government tourism through transportation and services. The people maintain cleanliness and comfort for tourists during their arrival to Indonesia and entrepreneurs or people who provide souvenirs, traditional fabrics, traditional cuisine, traditional dances, and other professions. Most respondents agreed with applying hospitality value to services, facilities such as friendly people, hotels, halal food, and drinking. Some tourists are not strict about the attributes of Islam in their chosen destination. This study confirms that Islamic Motivation significantly affects the satisfaction and loyalty of tourists. These findings are consistent with previous research that found that Islamic motivation is related to traveler's motivation to drive motivation and attract motivation.

7.1. Theoretical Implication

Tourism development in developing countries requires improving services to keep up with global trends. Tourist destinations must continue to innovate constantly, not only physically but also the values offered. Tourist destinations need to reposition the market to create new tourism destination products and services, maintain repeat visits, and stimulate new markets. From an economic perspective, tourist destinations are more than just geographical places that tourists visit.

7.2. Managerial Implication

The private or public sector can organize tourist destinations. The change in attitude on tourist destinations from merely "place" or "region" to "product" and even "experience gathering." It depends mostly on the point of view of various parties involved in it, such as local host communities, public administration, object destination managers, tourists, etc., who have diverse destinations and needs.

7.3. Policy Maker Implication

As a sustainable industry based on spirituality, economic tourism, which is the principle to "sell" tourism, impacts tourism management. Tourism has a long-term pattern, so it requires integrative studies of various components of actors, governments, manufacturers, art activists, hotel managers, transportation owners, communities, schools, and universities.

8. Conclusions

Religious tourism is respectful of the availability of spiritual attributes such as halal food and drink, qibla directions, prayer mats, and even holly Qur'an provided by the hotel manager. Religious tourism includes the invitation of spirituality and encourages the improvement of economic trends through national foreign exchange. Many Muslim customers and travelers naturally prefer to continue practicing their beliefs during their travels and holidays, such as praying and consuming halal food and using products and services. Research on religious-based tourism contributes to the development of management concepts and methods.

9. Limitation and further research recommendation

Limitations in this study are still shortcomings; Bali and Jogjakarta's tourist destinations have cultural structures, customs, and habits of people with different religious majorities. For foreign tourists who vacation for a relatively long time feel less happy. R Square rate of 78.8% is with the criteria of moderate variable loyalty visits influenced by the attracting motivation, driving motivation, and motivation of Islamic attributes; unscamined variables affect the remaining 21.2%. Thus, so that the value of R Square in the criteria is good, > 80%. Halal tourism development advice in Bali is expected to be further improved, such as the availability

of Muslim places of worship, gender-specific separate toilets, and halal food for Muslim tourists' convenience. Researchers can then add unstudied variables such as general risk on trust, destination image, and so on. Researchers can then use the new analysis tools for more accurate results.

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Ethical Approval

This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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